

Smart Biofloc Monitoring System for Fish Farming

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Abstract— This project proposes a Biofloc Monitoring system that utilizes sensors, ESP8266 (ESP-01) wifi module integrated with Arduino UNO and Internet of Things technology to monitor water quality parameters to prioritize Fish growth and health. Biofloc fish farming needs a human to monitor the fish growing conditions but with the help of a Monitoring System, fish growing conditions can be monitored. Our system is an innovative solution that can be used to improve the sustainability and efficiency of aquaculture by integrating Internet of Things technology with real-time data monitoring. Monitoring optimal conditions for fish growth parameters like temperature, pH, Humidity, Gas Concentration, and turbidity is a challenge. This system uses sensors to gather information from Water with the help of the Arduino UNO microcontroller. The recorded data can be seen in LCD display and it is sent as real-time data to an IoT data storage and visualization platform. This system also shows alerts to farmers when Fish growth Condition parameters cross Ideal ranges in real time which helps to prevent issues like contamination of water and fish mortality. This can lead to optimization of water quality which can lead to faster fish growth and higher yields. This system can improve fish productivity and support the long-term sustainability of fish farming practices.

Keywords— " Monitoring, Sensors, Arduino, water quality, Biofloc".

I. INTRODUCTION

Biofloc is a modern technology that is gaining popularity due to its creative and innovative approach to fish farming practices. The Smart Biofloc Monitoring System for fish farming is a solution created to optimize and automate the management of fish farms by integrating Internet of Things sensors for sustainable farming practices. Freshwater Fishes like Tilapia, Rohu, and Katla can be grown using Biofloc Technology. The use of a Monitoring system for Fish Farming is discussed in this paper. In this project, five sensors are considered which are pH, Thermistor as temperature sensor, Humidity, MQ-135 gas, and turbidity. This system utilizes sensors and Internet of Things devices to continuously monitor key parameters in real-time. The data collected by the system in real-time using these sensors can be seen using LCD Display and it is sent to a data storage and visualization platform. The farmers can monitor and view the fish growth conditions in real-time from their own

mobiles. Alerts are also given when the parameters cross the optimal range for fish-growing conditions. This ensures optimal conditions for fish health and growth.

Fig1. Biofloc fish farming tank

Fig.2 Monitoring System attached to an actual Biofloc Tank

Here, Figure. 1 shows the Biofloc Fish tanks that are used in homes conventionally. Standard biofloc tank is circular or rectangular in shape having a height of 1.2 meters an area with a circumference of 4 meters and a capacity of 500 to 10,000 litres constructed using materials such as tarpaulin sheet, cement, fibre reinforced plastic. The Total Expenditure of a Biofloc tank ranges from rupees 55,000 to 60,000. Figure. 2 shows, how the sensors are attached to the biofloc tank. In this project, we will be using a circular bowl resembling a biofloc tank. We do not use an actual tank in our project. The sensors are kept inside or near a bowl full of water. Samples are also used to test in water. Our automated system provides precise monitoring and helps to increase productivity, reduce operational costs, and profitable fish farming practices. Biofloc monitoring system reduces the need for a human presence at all times. This paper mainly focuses on taking important parameters for monitoring and providing a dependable outcome, thus making the model simple, practical, and easily accessible to Fish Farmers.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Design and development of automation system for biofloc fish farming [1] by Phawa and co-authors designed and developed an automated biofloc fish farming system. To measure the water temperature, a temperature sensor has been used. Arduino board is used for processing and controlling a heater that is placed in the tank. E-monitoring system for biofloc fish farming [2] by Mahanjan and co-authors developed an e-monitoring system for the automated fish farming process. This system is integrated with IoT supported system for monitoring the fish farming process where PH sensors, Temperature sensors, TDS sensors, and Gas sensors. Smart Biofloc Monitoring System for Fish Farming Using Machine Learning [3] by Abid and co-authors have developed an IoT solution for monitoring Biofloc and gathering data. This system used low-cost sensors in our product to make it feasible for poor fish farmers. Multiple machine learning algorithms such as decision trees, random forest, support vector machine, logistic regression, and ensemble learning are applied to the collected dataset to effectively predict mortality. Smart IoT biofloc water management system using decision regression tree [4] by Mozumder and co-authors proposed a smart IoT based biofloc monitoring system that uses a number of sensors to collect, store, and analyze the data by using the decision regression tree model for forecasting the water condition. Design and development of smart system for biofloc fish farming in Bangladesh [5] by Goswami and co-authors presented a complete description of the equipment and things that are needed to build an ideal Biofloc System. The Authors suggest a cost-saving devices description to build a Biofloc water tank. IoT based smart water quality prediction for biofloc aquaculture [6] by Rashid and co-authors presented an IoT based water quality prediction system using sensors. It proposes an IoT-based solution to increase efficiency and productivity. It focuses on a machine learning based analysis for tracing water quality and sending notifications to the user as well. IoT based smart monitoring system for fish farming [7] by Ramya and co-authors developed another IoT based automated system that can not only monitor the fish farm but also assists fish farm owners by maintaining the fish feeding process. IoT-based real-time biofloc monitoring and controlling system [8] by Al Mamun and co-authors introduced a system that continuously analyzes biofloc regulating parameters, such as temperature, total dissolved solids (TDS), pH, turbidity, dissolved oxygen (DO), and water level to maintain the ideal circumstances for biofloc. An Internet of Things enabled platform was implemented to collect and analyze real-time data from sensors including the DS18B20 water temperature, pH-4502C, analog dissolved oxygen, analog total dissolved solids, and water level sensors. Their experiment was conducted with Nile tilapia. The ESP32 Micro-controller utilized Wi-Fi to process sensor data, enabling real-time data analysis on mobile and computer devices through a mobile application. If the temperature, water level, or dissolved oxygen changes from the expected value, a signal is sent to the Blynk. Biofloc technology: An overview and its application [9] by Ray and Mohanty propose that utilizing biofloc technology, an excellent alternative to traditional aquaculture can overcome the limiting factors of conventional fish farming while ensuring water quality smartly. It proposes that the aquaculture and fishing industry has become the second largest contributor to Bangladesh's

export earnings, contributing about 3.57 % to the country's GDP and approximately 1.24 % of the earnings in foreign exchange. Monitoring System can be very crucial as Biofloc fish farming has gained popularity in India as a sustainable aquaculture method which can be done in low-cost Investment that can potentially offer long-term profitability. Design of a smart biofloc monitoring and controlling system using IoT [10] by Tasnim and co-authors focus on developing an IoT based device for biofloc fish tanks to monitor various water quality parameters. It also controls water temperature and air pump. The proposed system device is comprised of Atmega 328P microcontroller, Node MCU, pH Sensor - pH-4502C, Temperature sensor - DH18B20, turbidity sensor, TDS sensor, LCD Monitor, and Air pump. Atmega 328P is used with ESP8266 module that links the embedded device to the internet and gathers the relevant data from temperature, analog pH and turbidity sensors. These sensed data go to the microcontroller. It focuses on users monitoring the water quality data received from sensors accordingly from any remote location through the user interface. IoT based aquaculture monitoring and control system [11] by Rosaline and Sathyalakshimi presented an IoT-based solution for Aquaculture monitoring. They presented a system using a temperature sensor, Ammonia sensor, Salinity sensor, water level sensor, Node MCU ESP12E controller, Wi-Fi controller, and web server for sending SMS. The measured values from the sensors are compared with the established data and an alert message is processed in the form of SMS through web server. It focuses on the growth of shrimp and fish. Design of smart biofloc for real time water quality management system [12] by I. Ahamed and A. Ahmed implemented a prototype of a biofloc farm monitoring system taking into consideration of the chemical properties of water and controlling the pumps as well. Internet of Things play a vital role to monitor and manage water quality to flourish the indoor Aquaculture Industry. It also proposes a mobile application was used for real-time monitoring and controlling as well.

III. PROBLEM DEFINITION

From the literature survey, we know that Biofloc tanks can use a monitoring system to monitor water quality instead of humans. There are number of water quality parameters. We learned from the study that all parameters need not be monitored, as the essential ones should be monitored. It might be possible to implement a system that is entirely automated, requires less human watch time, and is less costly. Raw data recorded in real-time is taken as real-time data. Water was monitored and recorded using IoT sensors. Our system integrates real-time Monitoring and Internet of Things technology to enhance fish health and improve fish farming productivity and efficiency

IV. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The proposed Smart Biofloc Monitoring System for Fish Farming consists of a Hardware Setup. The Hardware setup consists of sensors, Arduino UNO. The first step is collecting data of water quality parameters using various sensors. This system is used to record water quality parameters such as temperature, pH, gas levels, turbidity, and Humidity in real-time. Alerts are given using a buzzer when ideal range is crossed. A web or mobile application can be used by Fish Farmers to see the recorded data of the water quality

Parameters with a real-time monitoring and control. By record and Monitor of the parameters in real time, this System can be used to improve fish health, reduce resource consumption, and ensure efficient fish farming management. It is cost-efficient and reduces the need for a human presence at all times. This system makes real-time monitoring system without taking too many parameters into consideration and it is cost-efficient. This system is very useful for fish farmers as it can be used to monitor Fish Farming in real time by anyone, even without much technical knowledge.

V. DATASET

Live data is collected in real time by our system which can be viewed on LCD Display or Mobile Application. Sensors like pH, Temperature, gas, Humidity and turbidity is used to obtain the parameter values by integrating them with Arduino UNO. Using these input features, the water quality is monitored.

VI. METHODOLOGY

There are numerous factors that determine the water quality in biofloc Fish Farming Tanks. But to Monitor the Water quality, we have used the most important and required Parameters. This System primarily involves employing sensors to collect inputs from Water. This system IoT technology to optimize water quality, monitor water condition, and enhance biofloc management. A group of attributes that define Water quality are those that make the Water eligible for Fish growth. The evaluation of a few Parameters is necessary for Health of fish. The Conditions of Water quality should be monitored. We used inputs such as pH, gas, turbidity, Humidity, and temperature.

TABLE I. SENSORS AND THEIR RANGE VALUES

S.No	Sensors Used	
	Sensor Name	Range values
1	Humidity Sensor	50 –80
2	Temperature Sensor	23 –30
3	Turbidity Sensor	75 – 150 NTU
4	pH Sensor	6.8 – 8.0
5	Gas Sensor	0 –1.5

A group of characteristics that define water quality are those that make the Fish eligible for consumption. The evaluation of certain characteristics in water present in a biofloc tank is necessary. Temperature, pH, and turbidity, gas levels and Humidity are all monitored and examined using our system. pH levels should be maintained between 6.8 to 8. Higher pH levels is Fatal to Fishes which can cause the fishes to die. The ideal Turbidity for Water quality in biofloc Tanks is between 75 to 150 Nephelometric Turbidity Units (NTU). The Ideal Temperature for Water in biofloc Tanks should be at a consistent temperature of 23 to 30 degrees Celsius. The Humidity levels range from 5 to 50. The gas level is between 0 to 1.5 ppm. Higher levels are toxic to Fishes. Exceeding these values is one of the indications of poor Water quality.

Fig 3. Block diagram showing process of Smart Monitoring Biofloc Fish farming.

From fig. 3 We can clearly get an idea about the Recording and Monitoring of Water Quality Parameters.

Table 1 shows us that significant parameters to Monitor Water quality and its optimal value for good Biofloc Fish Farming. These are the range of values obtained although it is not completely accurate.

Fig 4: Hardware setup of the proposed solution

Here, figure 4 displays the hardware setup of this system. Sensor values from Water are measured and shown in this figure.

The Methodology of our project can be seen in Figure 3 which consists of the Hardware Setup. The power unit consists of a 12-volt Transformer which is to be used to step down AC voltage to 12 volts. Power is supplied as the Voltage Regulator converts 12 Volt AC into 5 Volt DC which is given to components. The Hardware Setup consists of Humidity sensor, PH sensor, Temperature sensor (Thermistor), Turbidity Sensor, Gas Sensor, LCD Display, Arduino UNO, Jumper wires, LM – 317 Voltage regulators, 12 Volt Step Down Transformer, ESP8266 (ESP-01) Wifi Module and buzzer. Thing view app and Arduino UNO are the only Software Requirements. Arduino UNO used with an ESP8266 (ESP-01) WiFi module links the system to the internet and gathers the data from temperature (Thermistor), pH, Humidity, mq-135 gas, and turbidity sensors.

These recorded data go to the microcontroller. It uses Internet of Things technology to monitor water conditions and enhance biofloc management. Arduino UNO is utilized to obtain the raw sensor readings. Sensors are then placed in water for several seconds to monitor and record water quality parameters that are used to predict and optimize conditions for biofloc growth. Samples like sand and sludge water are poured into the water to check variations in water quality. The recorded values are also displayed in LCD display. Threshold values are fixed for each sensor. A buzzer gives alerts when Ideal Water Quality conditions are exceeded. The obtained data is transmitted using the ESP8266 (ESP-01) WiFi module to an IoT data storage and visualization platform for storage and analysis. Thing view Application is used as it is free. The Channel name "IOT MONITOR" with Channel ID "1340960" is created to store the sensor's values. Recorded values are visualized in Charts. Finally, the Thing View web server or application can be used by Fish Farmers to see the recorded data of the water quality parameters with real-time monitoring and control. By recording and monitoring of parameters in real-time, this system is used to improve fish health and ensure efficient fish farming management.

VII. RESULTS

In the system, Arduino IDE was used to write the code for five sensors namely pH, temperature, Humidity, gas concentration and turbidity. Each sensor has to be provided with its individual codes for its functioning and these codes are written under one program for all the sensors to work synchronously. The image for which is shown in figure 5.

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Sketch Tools Help
Arduino Uno
TURB_PH_TEMP_IOTino
1 #include <LiquidCrystal.h>
2 LiquidCrystal lcd(8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13);
3 #include <Wire.h>
4 #include <SoftwareSerial.h>
5 SoftwareSerial espserial(6, 7); //wifi
6
7 #include "DHT.h"
8 #define DHTPIN1 A4
9 #define DHTTYPE DHT11 // DHT11 sensor type
10 DHT dht1(DHTPIN1, DHTTYPE);
11 int BUZ = 4;
12
13 String AP = "iotdata"; // CHANGE ME
14 String PASS = "12345678"; // CHANGE ME
15 String API = "6U1JC330818YAGuP";
16 String HOST = "api.thingspeak.com"; //*** 1340960Channel ID: ****/crisp123iot //CHANNEL 3
17 String PORT = "80";
18 int countTrueCommand;
    
```

Fig 5. Program in Arduino IDE

Water was taken in a bowl with few samples like sand and sludge water. All the sensors were properly arranged to obtain the data. The following figure 6 represents the working model of the system.

Fig 6. The working model

Once the power supply was given, the Arduino UNO starts functioning and the sensors are ready to capture the data. The sensor's readings were collected in real time which can be viewed as output in the LCD display as shown in figure 7.

Fig 7. LCD Display Output

Data collected from these sensors were transmitted using ESP8266 (ESP-01) Wifi module to a IoT Storage platform for visualization and analysis. Thing view application can be used to see the recorded data of the water quality parameters. The following representation, figures.8,9,10,11,12 show the output chart images of all the input parameters namely Temperature, Humidity, pH, gas concentrations and Turbidity.

Fig 8. Output MQ-135 Sensor value in Chart image

MQ stands for the gas sensor value recorded. Min indicates the minimum value recorded and max indicates the maximum recorded value. The date of recorded data is shown. The last seen time is also recorded as it is seen below each chart. The minimum value recorded with date and time can be seen. Maximum recorded value with data and time can also be seen.

Fig 9. Output Turbidity Sensor value in Chart image

TRU stands for the Turbidity sensor value recorded. Min indicates the minimum value recorded and max indicates the maximum recorded value. The date of recorded data is shown. The last seen time is also recorded as it is seen below each chart. The minimum value recorded with date and time can be seen. Maximum recorded value with data and time can also be seen.

Fig 10. Output Temperature Sensor (Thermistor) value in Chart image

TEMP stands for the Temperature sensor value recorded. Min indicates the minimum value recorded and max indicates the maximum recorded value. The date of recorded data is shown. The last seen time is also recorded as it is seen below each chart. The minimum value recorded with date and time can be seen. Maximum recorded value with data and time can also be seen.

Fig 11. Output Humidity Sensor value in Chart image

HUM stands for the Humidity sensor value recorded. Min indicates the minimum value recorded and max indicates the maximum recorded value. The date of recorded data is shown. The last seen time is also recorded as it is seen below each chart. The minimum value recorded with date and time can be seen. Maximum recorded value with data and time can also be seen.

Fig 12. Output sensor values in Chart images

PH stands for the pH sensor value recorded. Min indicates the minimum value recorded and max indicates the maximum recorded value. The date of recorded data is shown. The last seen time is also recorded as it is seen below each chart. The minimum value recorded with date and time can be seen. Maximum recorded value with data and time can also be seen.

In the app, charts display the parameters as PH stands for pH, HUM stands for humidity, TRU stands for turbidity, MQ stands for gas and TEMP stands for temperature. Min indicates the minimum value recorded and max indicates the maximum recorded value. The date of recorded data is shown. The last seen time is also recorded as it is seen below each chart. The minimum value recorded with date and time can be seen. Maximum recorded value with data and time can also be seen. The graphs also show the timeframe of real-time data recorded on various dates. This is how the system works. Our system shows that biofloc fish farming can be monitored easily by a monitoring system.

VIII. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, a Biofloc Monitoring System for Fish Farming is proposed to Monitor Fish Growth conditions. Fishes consumed through Biofloc Farming Method should be of high-quality under right Growing Conditions. Biofloc is a great and advanced approach in Fish Farming and our Monitoring system is very useful and supportive to Biofloc Fish Farming. IOT Sensors are used in the Fish Farming practices to evaluate the Water quality. By integrating real-time data collection and Analysis, we can optimize water quality and ensure efficient ways to improve fish health. This system has minimal operational costs, making it a great appliance for modern fish farming practices by improving fish farming efficiency, productivity, and sustainability.

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